

Democratising Scientific Software in Physics Education: AI-Assisted Custom Instrumentation for Teachers

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Abstract.

Published Arduino-based mechanics experiments reveal a continued accessibility paradox: while sensor hardware costs are minimal, the software required for instrumentation control and data analysis can be financially restrictive for school practitioners, limiting access to enhanced analytical techniques.

This paper contributes to addressing this gap by showing how AI-assisted Python development enables KS4–5 secondary school physics teachers, without formal programming training, to extend Arduino-based experiments using entirely free software. A worked example is presented in which a complete graphical user interface for spring oscillation measurements is developed with large language models. The development process, challenges encountered, and implications for classroom practice are discussed.

The resulting system provides real-time data acquisition, automated analysis, and data visualisation, including curve fitting to anharmonic oscillator models and numerical derivative calculations. Static and dynamic spring constant measurements show good agreement ($19.94 \pm 0.13 \text{ N,m}^{-1}$ and $20.44 \pm 0.14 \text{ N,m}^{-1}$ respectively), validating the approach.

The method generalises to a wide range of Arduino-based experiments and demonstrates that sophisticated data acquisition and analysis are now accessible to individual educators at low cost. A short demonstration video of the apparatus and workflow is available at <https://zenodo.org/records/17980784>.

key words: Arduino, artificial intelligence (AI), ChatGPT, DeepSeek, Scientific software development, ESP32, large language models (LLMs), graphical user interface (GUI), microcontroller, Python, 'vibe coding'.

1. Introduction

The use of microcontrollers in the physics classroom—the most commonplace platform now being "Arduino"[‡]—offers a relatively inexpensive route for introducing innovative

[‡] the encompassing term "Arduino" is used to mean microcontrollers which are compatible with being programmed under the Arduino integrated development environment (IDE).

ways of making physical measurements, and as a recent literature survey of Arduino [1] highlighted, oscillations, waves, thermodynamics, electricity and magnetism and mechanics proved particularly popular areas for application. Pertinently here are the historical studies reported for oscillating springs ([2], [3], [4] [5]), using HC-SR04 ultrasonic/OriginLab 9, HC-SR04 ultrasonic/GeoGebra, vertical linear array of ir reflection sensors/Mathematica, and HC-SR04 ultrasonic/Mathematica as sensor(s)/data fitting tool, respectively.

Becker et al have addressed the educational opportunities and challenges of AI code generation [6] and although AI has begun to reach some classrooms, this tends to be focussed on teacher-related roles [7]. We also see the recognition of the use of AI for developing Arduino code [8], however, relatively little attention has been given to the use of AI as a practical development aid for enabling low-cost experimental apparatus suitable for classroom use. Beyond demonstrating functional instrumentation, this work documents the AI-assisted development process itself, providing realistic expectations for educators considering similar projects.

Data collection and display rarely garners much discussion within report documentation. The Arduino IDE has limited graphical display capabilities: its serial plotter will show data in a graphical form but cannot save the data but the Arduino Serial Monitor with Logging (IDE 2.x only) allows saving serial output to a file. Other zero cost options include: Putty [9] for monitoring the serial data stream whilst Tera Term [10] can also perform basic plotting, as can CoolTerm [11] and all can be used in combination with a spreadsheet for data analysis and graphing. Parallax Data Acquisition [12] is older software which is an add-in for Microsoft Excel and although initially for Parallax microcontrollers, has been made compatible with Arduino by its community. However, it's compatibility with newer versions of Microsoft Excel might require changes in some software settings for it to run.

Notable commercial software with greater versatility for data collection, graphical user interface design and analysis includes Matlab [13], Labview [14], daqInsight [15], and Megunolink [16] whilst the school-focussed Microsoft Data Streamer [17] although free, does require an Office 365 subscription.

Here, a bespoke graphical user interface (GUI) is described, managing the collection, graphical display, numerical analysis and saving of data to a file on the host computer. The programming language used is the open source cross-platform general-purpose language Python [18], a highly versatile system and frequently used by the professional scientific community and, indeed, is the programming language of choice [19] within Secondary education in England. Python also allows the design of graphical user interfaces through its user interface (GUI) library Tkinter[20] and is what will be used here.

Implementing a graphical user interface for an application has, until recently, not been a trivial task, requiring a significant degree of programming skills. This situation is changing considerably with the development of 'vibe coding' - a method of developing computer code whereby artificial intelligence (AI) is used to generate code whilst the

user describes in natural language the required functionality to the artificial intelligence either in written or spoken language, and the AI returns the code. By reciprocating interactions between the AI and developer, the code can be refined, issues solved and code extended as required. The GUI application developed here was 'vibe-coded' using the (zero-cost versions) large language artificial intelligence models ChatGPT [21] and DeepSeek [22].

The target audience for the making of devices is likely to be for the KS4-5 teacher, although there is no reason the principles discussed here are used in an after-school time enrichment activity for their learners.

2. The Static and Dynamic Spring Constants

In a static measurement, the magnitude of the displacement, x , of a spring in response to an applied force F is governed by the springs spring constant, k (Equation 1).

$$F = -kx \quad (1)$$

leading to a simple way of measuring the static force constant (Equation 2) by measuring displacement as a function of force.

$$k = \frac{F}{x} \quad (2)$$

The time-dependent amplitude of a spring oscillating in simple harmonic motion offers an alternative method of determining the spring constant, the dynamical spring constant.

Considering the general equation for the angular frequency ω of a mass-spring system:

$$\omega = \sqrt{\frac{k}{m}} \quad (3)$$

where k is the spring force constant (spring stiffness), and m is the mass attached to the spring. Rearranging (3)

$$k = m\omega^2 \quad (4)$$

thus,

$$k = m \left(\frac{2\pi}{T} \right)^2 = \frac{4\pi^2 m}{T^2} \quad (5)$$

For the work here, T , the time period of oscillation, is experimentally determined, as is the mass, m , thus application of Equation (5) allows for determination of the dynamical spring constant. As the reader will discover, using Python, this raw experimental data, can be used to mathematically and graphically generate other behaviours, specifically here not only the time dependence of displacement but also the first and second derivatives, velocity and acceleration with respect to time.

3. Method

3.1. Hardware

Figure 1: The circuit board and components for the measuring device. For clarity, the pin designations for the ESP32C3 (supermini) are shown and the VL53L0X pin designations on the measuring device are written on the right-most of the figure.

A VL53L0X[23] distance-measuring time-of-flight (ToF) laser-ranging sensor was wired to an ESP32C3 [24] board on a piece of matrix board (Figure 1). The maximum data measurement speed was notionally 33 Hz. A wired connection between the microcontroller and the computer’s USB port provided both power to the microcontroller and thence the VL53L0X and serial communications. Connection from the sensor to the microcontroller uses the inter-integrated circuit I²C [25] protocol. The demands of the system are low and other microcontrollers which have I2C capabilities could have been used equally.

3.2. Software

All code referenced below as supplementary files SF1, SF2, SF3 SF4 and SF5 may be freely downloaded from here: <https://zenodo.org/records/17980934> .

The graphical user interface (GUI)-based Python program/script was developed on a computer with a Linux operating system using Python 3.12.3 and the necessary libraries. The free-to-use versions of large language artificial intelligence models ChatGPT [21] and DeepSeek [22] were used to develop the code. Writing, compiling and programming of the microcontroller was carried out using the Arduino IDE (v 2.3.6) [26]. The ESP32 code for distance/time measurements can be found in Supplementary File SF1.

3.2.1. Starting out: How do we use Python to display data from an Arduino?

In order to assess how a novice might be able to start a project such as this, an initial rather broad question was posed to ChatGPT : "How can Python be used to display data from an Arduino?": the full response is given in Supplementary File SF2.

ChatGPT's response is detailed, instructing how to write an Arduino programme to read analogue voltage and provides two Python scripts, the first to list readings of the pin voltage over time and the second to plot the varying voltage with time. This combined example provides a useful springboard for the novice to explore Python as a means of communicating with and receiving data from a microcontroller and plotting of data. It should be borne in mind that pin designations will depend upon the specific microcontroller used and the com port label will depend upon the operating system used (Windows uses COM1, COM2, etc whereas Linux uses port assignments /dev/ttyS0, /dev/ttyS1, etc and usb serial devices as /dev/ttyUSB0, /dev/ttyUSB1, etc). Serial speed can be set over a relatively wide range (115200 baud is a commonly set speed) but most importantly, must be the same in Arduino code and Python scripts.

3.2.2. From Springboard Example to Application

The springboard example (described above) is built upon and modified in three successive stages each using the same ESP32 time-distance measurement program (Supplementary File SF1). The guiding principle throughout is not merely incremental complexity but systematic validation, establish that core functionality works correctly in the simplest possible environment before adding GUI complexity; thus the workflow followed:

(i) Stage 1: Terminal script with graphics (Supplementary File SF3)

This script is executed from the command line with no GUI, but implements complete data collection, processing, and visualisation:

- Connects to ESP32 and reads serial data for specified duration
- Saves data with metadata to timestamped files
- Calculates equilibrium position from collected data
- Plots distance vs time with equilibrium line marked (Figure 2, bottom)

This establishes that the core physics and data processing functions work correctly. The terminal environment is simple and as was learned when the GUI was implemented, more complex code is required to handle events §. Further, this automation of analysis of data can be confirmed correct in the first instance by manual plotting of a saved datafile, manually plotting data and determining number of oscillations. The average time period and displacements can be roughly checked by comparing with a rule. This validation step is critical for AI-assisted development. When a GUI version (Stage 2 or

§ such as threading complexity (allowing the program to handle GUI responsiveness while collecting data."), addition of button event handlers and display updates

Stage 3) inevitably encounters problems, we know they arise from GUI implementation rather than underlying physics calculations and results, thereby simplifying debugging when errors arise. The code organisation(s) reflects the iterative development process rather than idealised structure, however, comprehensive inline comments enable readers to trace functionality.

The functions/components and descriptions for this Stage 1 terminal-based code are given in Table 1. although it should be noted that the last entry ("Graphical interface (Tkinter)") does not apply in this first stage only Stage 2). The graphical output would be identical to that shown in Figure 2 (bottom picture) which although it is data from the initial GUI version of the code, is identical in its core behaviour.

(ii) Stage 2: Basic GUI (Supplementary File SF4)

The working terminal script is now wrapped in a Tkinter GUI framework (Figure 2, top). Critically, the core data collection and analysis functions remain identical—only the user interface changes from command-line prompts to buttons:

- 'Start Data Collection' button replaces 'Press Enter to start'
- 'Stop Collection Early' button enables manual termination
- 'Plot Data' button replaces 'Press Enter to plot'

The essential functions (`find_esp32_port`, `read_and_save_data`, `save_data_to_file`, `plot_data`) are unchanged from Stage 1 and all the function/descriptions given in Table 1. are appropriate (for Stage 1, the last entry in Table 1. ("Graphical interface (Tkinter)" does not apply) This isolation of changes is deliberate—if GUI buttons do not work, we know the problem is GUI implementation, not physics calculations which were already validated. This stage introduces threading complexity: data collection must run in a background thread to prevent the GUI from freezing. Successful coding for threading required a number of AI iterations, and clearly shows the necessity of the cyclical nature of AI-human collaboration to solve more complex problems.

(iii) Stage 3: Enhanced analytical GUI (Supplementary File SF5)

Only after establishing that both core functionality (Stage 1) and basic GUI operation (Stage 2) work correctly are advanced features added:

- Real-time countdown display during collection
- Idle-mode distance averaging when not collecting
- File retrieval and reanalysis capability
- Anharmonic oscillator curve fitting
- Calculation and plotting of derivatives (velocity, acceleration)
- User-adjustable mass and collection time parameters

Each enhancement is added individually, tested with physics validation, and refined before proceeding to the next. For example, if the now introduced curve capability fitting

fails, we know the problem is in the curve fitting implementation—not in data collection (validated Stage 1) or initial GUI framework (validated at Stage 2).

The final GUI is shown in Figure 3 (top) and typical measurement output in Figure 4. whilst the Python script can be found as Supplementary File 5. and a brief description of the functions described in Table 2.

3.3. AI-Assisted Development Workflow

Code development which has been described above, followed an iterative pattern: initial implementations were tested against physics expectations, debugging cycles addressed failures, and refinements improved performance. ChatGPT proved effective for initial code generation but showed limitations as complexity grew, often producing incomplete outputs. DeepSeek maintained better coherence across longer iterations, generating complete code particularly for threading and GUI event handling. The process required tens of hours comprising exploration of AI capabilities, incremental function building with validation, and debugging cycles. The human role was continuous: testing implementations, validating physics, identifying problems, and clarifying requirements to AI. Clear prompt engineering proved critical—ambiguous requests produced poor results regardless of AI capability. Development was non-linear: features were sometimes removed and rebuilt when initial approaches proved problematic. This iterative collaboration characterizes the accessible pathway: not simple specification followed by perfect code, but genuine partnership where human judgment and AI capability shape outcomes together.

Function / Component	Description
<code>find_esp32_port</code>	Searches the computer's USB connections to find where the ESP32 is plugged in.
<code>read_and_save_data</code> (<i>collect live serial data</i>)	Opens the USB link to the ESP32, gathers measurements from its live data stream for the specified time, and afterwards calls <code>save_data_to_file</code> to store the results.
<code>save_data_to_file</code>	Writes the collected measurements and metadata (mass, run duration) to a uniquely named text file on the Desktop, then returns the file location.
<code>plot_data</code>	Opens the saved file, calculates the spring's average (equilibrium) position and the number of oscillations, and displays a graph of motion over time with the equilibrium line marked.
<code>main</code>	Guides the user through the terminal-based process: press Enter to start collecting data, wait while readings are taken, then press Enter again to view the plot.
Graphical interface (Tkinter)	Added to the basic script using AI assistance (ChatGPT). Creates a window with buttons to replace the Enter-key prompts: "Start Data Collection", "Stop Early", and "Plot Data". Handles threading and pop-up messages so the app remains responsive while data is being collected. This demonstrates how a simple script can be progressively converted into a user-friendly GUI.

Table 1: Description of the main functions in the ESP32 spring-motion data collection program (Stages 1 and 2: Supplementary Files SF3 and SF4). Note: The Graphical interface (Tkinter) entry applies only to Stage 2.

Figure 2: Stage 2 GUI (top) and graphical output (bottom). Stage 1 graphical output would be identical (not shown separately) since the core data collection and plotting code is the same in all three stages.

4. Results

Dynamic spring constants (Table 3.) closely match the static values (Figure 5.) The standard error of the mean for all sets of dynamic spring constants gives a final value of $k=20.44\pm 0.14$ N/m and for the static experiment (y -intercept = 8.969 ± 0.037 , slope = -19.941 ± 0.130) $k=19.94\pm 0.13$ N/m. For the lightest mass, the measured constant is slightly smaller, but the difference is minor and within experimental spread.

Function	Description
<code>find_esp32_port</code>	Finds the serial port connected to the ESP32 by searching for <code>ttyACM</code> or <code>ttyUSB</code> devices.
<code>main</code>	Creates and runs the GUI, including all buttons, labels, and idle averaging.
<code>save_data_to_file</code>	Saves collected data and metadata to a uniquely named file in a 'Spring' folder on the Desktop.
<code>idle_average</code>	Continuously reads distance data from the ESP32 when not actively collecting, and calculates a running average displayed in the GUI.
<code>anharmonic_oscillator</code>	Defines the mathematical model for an anharmonic oscillator used to fit the collected spring motion data.
<code>start_data_collection</code>	Initiates data collection from the ESP32 in a separate thread, stops idle averaging, and updates GUI with live data and remaining time.
<code>stop_data_collection</code>	Stops the data collection process manually.
<code>plot_collected_data</code>	Waits for data to be saved, then calls <code>plot_data</code> to create plots.
<code>plot_data</code>	Reads saved data, calculates equilibrium position, counts zero crossings, estimates oscillation period and spring constant, fits an anharmonic oscillator model, and plots distance, speed (1st derivative), and acceleration (2nd derivative) over time.
<code>buttons</code>	Provides GUI buttons for Connect & Collect, Stop Collection, Plot Data, Exit, Retrieve & Analyze File, Update Mass, and Update Time.
<code>information</code>	Dynamically displays averaged distance from the sensor and remaining collection time in the GUI.

Table 2: Functions in the final GUI application (Stage 3: Supplementary File SF5) and their descriptions.

5. Conclusion

The rapid evolution of artificial intelligence presents a transformative opportunity to democratise access to advanced scientific instrumentation in education. This work demonstrates that through structured, iterative AI-human collaboration, educators without formal programming expertise can create low-cost, capable measurement tools

Figure 3: The refined final GUI for Spring Measurements.

Mass (kg)	k_1 (Nm ⁻¹)	k_2 (Nm ⁻¹)	k_3 (Nm ⁻¹)	Error s (Nm ⁻¹)
0.607	20.69	20.71	20.54	0.085
0.507	20.88	21.43	21.90	0.515
0.407	20.23	20.23	20.69	0.266
0.307	20.57	20.28	20.11	0.234
0.207	20.31	20.18	20.16	0.079
0.107	19.41	19.73	19.89	0.242

Table 3: Dynamic spring constant for various spring loads, including the standard deviation of three repeated measurements for each mass.

that enhance experimental physics teaching.

The successful development and validation of a Python/Tkinter GUI for spring constant measurements—yielding excellent agreement between static and dynamic methods (19.94 ± 0.13 N/m vs. 20.44 ± 0.14 N/m)—confirm the technical viability of the AI-assisted pathway described. More significant than the specific application, however, is the demonstrated development methodology: a staged, iterative process that deliberately isolates core physical functionality from interface complexity. This approach ensures that even partial implementations deliver immediate pedagogical value.

A realistic understanding of this collaboration is essential. Development was

Figure 4: Top: oscillation data , bottom: Time-series data showing distance, velocity (first derivative), and acceleration (second derivative) from anharmonic oscillator fit for the above data

not a simple matter of specification and execution; it required continuous human judgment—testing implementations, validating physics, and guiding AI with clear prompts—through tens of hours of iterative refinement. The process highlighted the complementary strengths of different AI tools: ChatGPT for initial code generation and DeepSeek for maintaining coherence across more complex tasks like threading and event handling.

Critically, educators need not achieve the sophistication of the final GUI. Like climbers who choose their stopping point, teachers can halt at any functional

Figure 5: Force vs Distance with best fit line $F = -19.94x + 8.97$ N. Note for each force, there are three measurements (overlapping) for each approximate distance.

stage—whether at basic data capture, simple plotting, or terminal-based analysis—and still gain meaningful, enhanced capability. This incremental, accessible pathway fundamentally lowers the barrier to custom scientific software development.

Beyond technical empowerment, this work fosters AI literacy within the teaching profession, aligning with broader STEM/STEAM [27] agendas by integrating computational tools into experimental practice. While focused on oscillating springs, the methodology generalises to a wide range of Arduino-based experiments, opening new avenues for collaborative creativity and custom instrumentation in the physics classroom.

To encourage adoption, all hardware designs and software code are provided under open licences. Educators can deploy a functional system directly or adapt it through the same AI-assisted workflow, turning a previously specialist task into an accessible, creative endeavour for teachers and students alike.

Acknowledgement of AI Contribution

The software code presented in this article was generated almost entirely through interaction with AI tools (ChatGPT and DeepSeek). Structural and framing suggestions were developed through discussion with the AI tool Claude [28]. However, the AI operated strictly under the author’s direction, with the development process guided by the author’s understanding of the physics involved, the educational aims of the project and structure required for functional implementation.

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Data availability

All data supporting this publication, including analysis of sample datasets and supplementary code are available at <https://zenodo.org/records/18000966>. Raw spring data can be made available upon reasonable request.

Ethics statement

This study did not involve human participants or animals.

Conflict of interest

The author declares no competing financial or personal interests.